

Report

**“IMPACT OF MARKETIN STRATEGY ON CONSUMER PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR. A
STUDY ON SAMSUNG ELECTRONIC IN NCR REGION”**

**FOR THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
FOR THE AWARD OF
MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION**

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

**Submitted to
Prof. (Sankar Mukherjee)**

**Submitted By
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**Enrolment Number
202010366
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**GALGOTIAS
UNIVERSITY**

**School of Business
Galgotias University**

DECLARATION

This is certify **Rahul kumar**, the student of **GALGOTIAS UNIVERSITY** studying in MBA has submitted a project report on the title “**IMPACT OF MARKETIN STRATEGY ON CONSUMER PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR. A STUDY ON SAMSUNG ELECTRONIC IN NCR REGION**” assigned by the university, for the partial fulfilment of the degree of Master of Business Administration (MBA).

I solemnly declare that the work done by me is original and no copy of it has been submitted to any other university for award of any other, degree, diploma, and fellowship on similar title.

Rahul Kumar

Signature of the Candidate

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

To list who all have helped me is difficult because they are so numerous and the depth is so enormous.

I would like to acknowledge the following as being idealistic channels and fresh dimensions in the completion of this project.

I take this opportunity to thank the University o for giving me a chance to do this project.

I take this opportunity to thank our Coordinator **Prof. (Sankar Mukherjee)**

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I would like to thank my College Library, for having provided various reference books andmagazines related to my project.

Lastly, I would like to thank each and every person who directly or in directly helped me in theCompletion of the project especially My Parents and Peers who supported me through out my Project.

ABSTRACT

Manufacturers of electronic brands tend to focus on technology with little consideration for customer needs. We have researched customer preference in order to learn more about customer needs in an effort to reduce the gap between technology and customer-needs. Customer behavior is defined in this study as buying behavior. This study aims at ascertaining the Consumer perception towards Samsung brand. A formal survey has been conducted in order to gathered the information required for this study. 100 responses have been collected for this study using online survey facility. This study will be helpful to understand how a consumer think about an electronic product and what are the main factors influenced a consumer to buy an electronic brand's product.

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CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

The color television industry in NCR has seen a dramatic change during the past one decade as liberalization and globalization showed its original face in full swing in the NCR sub-continent, making its market highly competitive and customer driven. A good number of TV customers today face a lot of dilemma at the time of taking a purchase decision to choose the brand because a number of substitutes are available in the market. As a result of this, the manufacturers are now forced to behave like price takers rather than price makers. Under the circumstances, it is quite obvious that the companies will have to do more homework to respond to the needs and tastes of the customers in order to survive in this competitive market. When it comes to the purchase decision of the TV customers, it depends on various product differentiation attributes such as price, game and goodwill of the company, design and appearance, digital function, after sales service, durability and warranty, power efficiency, financial incentives (free gifts, discounts and installments etc.), easy availability and smooth functioning.

It is an accepted fact that the generation of information plays an important role in the field of policy formation, marketing planning, strategy making and it also bridges the game between the buyers and the sellers. This study may provide the TV companies with a launch pad and act as a guide that can help same in chalking out strategies to enlarge the market share and also enhance the level of awareness among customers. In short, it can be claimed to be an accurate and timely report that may help them to gain a competitive edge over their customers.

Therefore, the present study aims at ascertaining the television customer's preference over the various counts of T.V. brands they use. The study also throws light on the customer's purchase behavior with respect to color television. This study may provide the T.V. companies with a launch pad and act as a guide that can help the same in chalking out strategies to enlarge market share and also enhance the level of awareness among customers and may help them to gain a competitive edge over their competitors.

The leading companies like Samsung, LG and others by introducing brands at various price points have effectively segmented the market which has resulted faster market expansion and penetration and

increased volumes. Product differentiation and innovative marketing efforts have resulted in attracting more and more customers to their brands. In fact, competition in the rural market has assumed battle field dimension and a battle for survival of the fittest. Therefore, in the light of the scenario where the marketing environment is changing at a very fast pace and the heightened aggression on the players in the television industry in NCR, it is therefore most appropriate to conduct a study on various

Major Factors influencing buyer Behavior

1: Culture Factor:

- Cultural factors comprise of set of values and ideologies of a particular community or group of individuals.
- As in USA mostly people prefer smart phones while in developing countries like NCR and SOUTH AFRICA their people prefer simple mobile phones

Culture is major characteristic to understand the consumer behavior. It will reveal the values of a particular society. An individual decides to behave in particular manner because of his or her culture. All these values that individual gets from his family. Every individual has their own set of values compare with others. What they use to do and see from their childhood will start to practice as a habit and those practices become their culture. Culture is various from individual to individual, country to country and region to region. Therefore, marketers should pay attention in analyzing the culture of variety of region to region and country to country to sell their products effectively. Moreover, throughout the process consumer is always under his culture as his or her family, society, status and friends influence him.

For a certain brand name such as Samsung smart phones it is important to understand cultural factors intrinsic to each Country's market in order to adjust its product development and marketing strategies. Understanding these facts Samsung is always doing the best to remain their brand number one in Asian market as well as in the world market. Samsung galaxy S8 plus and Samsung 49" RU7100 4K UHD Flat Smart TV is the recent and new addition to the market in this way. For instance, countries such as

china, NCR, south Korea, Philippine, Thailand, Indonesia and Sri Lanka etc. which is culturally has a great attraction and emotional attachment with music, pictures and compare with western countries. Considering these cultural effects Samsung introducing more features with their every new smart phone to the world. That is how Samsung smart phones and LED keep their brand name number one in Asian market and they are targeting young crowd who have a passion on music and videos. Therefore, considering that cultural effect Samsung has increase the sound quality in Samsung S8 plus latest smart phone feature high-quality 32-bit PCM and DSD64/128 playback and also increase the Video Quality and features like Picture Engine, UHD Engine, PQI (Picture Quality Index) 1400, HDR 10+, HLG (Hybrid Log Gamma), Mega Contrast, Pure Color,

Contrast Enhancer, Auto Motion Plus, Film Mode plus latest smart service like Bixby, Works with Google Assistant, Smart Things App Support, Smart Things, Gallery.

Consumer behavior is the study of how individual customers, groups or organizations select, buy, use, and dispose ideas, goods, and services to satisfy their needs and wants. It refers to the actions of the consumers in the marketplace and the underlying motives for those actions. The increasing trend in Smartphone among the people is the main reason that has amplified the interest to research on the topic. People's obsession about the Smartphone has been increasing rapidly. The aim of this research is therefore to find out consumer behavior of Smartphone buyers in NCRn Market. The research is trying to find out that why do people desire to purchase a Smartphone, what influence people in purchasing a Smartphone and what motivate them in making the purchase decision. Different consumers have different characteristics in their life that also influences their buying behavior. Social factors such as family, groups, roles and status) and personal factors (such as age, occupation, lifestyle, personality and self-concept) are those characteristics that could influence the buyer behavior in making final decision.

Top of the mind awareness is highest for brands like SAMSUNG. Evaluation criteria are generally a

mix of attribute based and attitude based. Consumers who are brand loyal use attitude based evaluation criteria and are involved in limited decision-making process. Whereas consumers who are purchasing their first smart phone and are tech savvy use attribute based evaluation criteria and are involved in extensive decision-making process. Consumers are basically looking for brand and value for money. Brand loyal consumers use lexicographic decision rule. Whereas others use disjunctive decision rule. 5) Outlet selection – consumers generally visit stores like SAMSUNG to have a look and feel of the phone and comparing prices. However, brand loyal consumers purchased from exclusive stores and consumers looking for value for money purchased from stores providing incentives such as extended warranty and freebies. 6) Post purchase behavior – consumers are generally satisfied with brands like SAMSUNG. These consumers are engaged in positive WOM. Whereas consumers are dissatisfied with both the product and after sales service offered for Motorola products. These consumers are involved in negative WOM which is diluting the brand value.

2: Social Factor:

The facts and experiences that influence individuals' personality, attitudes and lifestyle.

Family

If a teenager purchases a mobile he would prefer more of entertainments & games, while an official corporate will prefer more on presentation and professional mobiles.

Reference Group

For Example: semi wanted to purchase a mobile so he went to the nearby store and purchased a Samsung mobile because his friends and colleague were using same mobile and they were satisfied by it. • For e.g. Customer will buy a mobile from his relative or friend so he can get good guidance and good services.

Roles and Status

Each individual plays a dual role in the society depending on the group he belongs to. • As a C.E.O of a company he will buy such a mobile which can help him to play both the role properly i.e., C.E.O of the company as well as father of a child.

3: Psychological Factors

Motivation

Mostly people are attracted towards advertise of Samsung galaxy S3 mobile and are motivated to purchase the same.

Believes and Attitudes

Some people purchase Samsung smart phones to over show their beliefs and attitude towards their companions. • Example: - buy a Samsung galaxy S3 rather than Nokia Lumia.

Perception

For instance, two students want to purchase a Samsung galaxy note and S3 but one. Instead of being motivated by same purpose still they purchased different types of mobile. Because one pursued that note is best for its screen size and latter one pursued that S3 is best for style as well as sensor.

4: Personal Factors:

Age and family life cycle stage

Consumption of Samsung mobile is also affected by the stages of family life cycle like bachelor stage, newly married couple, young & old couple and independent children uses different Samsung phone according to their uses.

Life style

A person's lifestyle is reflected by in his activities hobbies, opinions & thinking as a man believing in simple living and high thinking will purchase Samsung wave y while a man living luxurious life will purchase Samsung galaxy note.

Occupation

Consumption is also influenced by the occupation of the consumer. A labor employee will purchase Samsung guru while at the top most level of the organization head will purchase Samsung infuse 4g.

Personality

Personality means some total of appearance, knowledge and different types of skills. That's why a man believing in innovation will go for S3 while a person loving indigenous product may purchase simple android phone.

“Social class “influence in Samsung devices consumers buying behavior

Social class determined the consumer behavior which they belong. Human beings are social animals and social class are variable according to lineage, education, occupation, income, wealth, residence and socio-cultural class. Usually in social class people who have similar values, behavior and lifestyle can be categorize together. As a Samsung marketer need to pay attention regarding this factor because the buying behavior of electronic device consumers in a certain social class to some extent is similar even though level of influences may be low or high, marketing strategies can be measure according to difference social class. Social perception is a major assign that influences the individuals buying behavior. For instance, a person who getting a low income may focus on price

when they make the decision of purchase. On the other hand, the person who getting higher income always considering the quality and uniqueness of the product. An individual who influenced by a social group which he is not belongs but like to connect with others such as in NCR in a peoples who is no need to buy an electronic device automatically tend to buy a Samsung device when he or she need to be a part of that group and be accepted by them.

Social Status

Social status of a consumer usually comprises of an individual's attitude, class and prestige. Its depends how he or she carries themselves socially or the position where they work or family background which they come or even the groups of friends they have. Social status depends on individual's consumption pattern. Those days it used to be jewelry, houses, cloths and vehicles to show social status of individuals but, in 20th century electronic devices indicate the social status. Especially when younger generation individual need to buy a phone, he or she always go for the latest electronic device in the market with latest and advanced fetchers. That is why Samsung always keep updating their devices brands year by year. Because its largely influence in consumers purchasing behavior.

How Social Influences on Consumer Behavior improve Marketing Strategies

It is important to understand how consumers feel and select products for their use, how consumers influenced by their culture, social class, media and environment and how they rank of product importance. As a Samsung manufacturer always use social media tools to television and media advertising in influence the consumer's decision making process. Also, Samsung try to engage with their consumers in activities like gaming and competitions for promotions of their products. In addition, Apple is the main competitor of the Samsung and however up to now apple couldn't touch the Samsung Asian market consumers because of the huge demand for Samsung devices from Asian consumers. Sometimes if a person is using Samsung device he is aware about the features of it and he will automatically force to buy a same brand to other friends.

Psychological Factors

Motivation

Consider Maslow's [Heirarchy of Needs](#). All humans are motivated by basic needs such as food and shelter, as well as higher-level psychological needs and self-fulfillment. These needs are innate in all of us and we are internally-motivated to achieve them at all costs, making it helpful when trying to understand the thought process of yourself or others.

Mostly people are attracted towards advertise of Samsung devices and are motivated to purchase the same.

Beliefs and Attitudes

Attitudes and beliefs are also important factors of consumer behavior. 'Attitudes' refers to a consumer's outlook on a certain brand, product, or service. Attitudes are commonly influenced by social factors. 'Beliefs' refers to a consumer's views on brands, products, or services, that is based on actual factual knowledge or personal opinion. Marketers should pay close attention to consumer attitudes and beliefs to ensure that consumers have an accurate view on the product or service in question, and if they don't, then the marketer would know to focus campaigns on correcting the false beliefs.

Some people purchase Samsung device to over show their beliefs and attitude towards their companions. • Example: - buy a Samsung galaxy rather than Nokia phone.

Perception

Perception also plays a vital role in consumer behavior. Perception is the way that individuals select and organize information in order to develop their own meaningful sense of the world. Three important components of perception are selective attention, selective retention, and selective comprehension. Each of these affects the ways consumers perceive information in a unique way.

For instance, two students want to purchase a Samsung galaxy note and S3 but one. Instead of being motivated by same purpose still they purchased different types of mobile. Because one pursued that note is best for its screen size and latter one pursued that S3 is best for style as well as sensor.

Learning

If a person is using a device of Samsung Company. He is mostly aware about feature of the Samsung device he will force other consumer to buy a same brand of device.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The main aim of marketing is meet and satisfy target customers need and wants buyer behavior refers to the peoples or organization conduct activities and together with the impact of various influence on them towards making decision on purchase of product and service in a market. the field of consumer behavior studies how individuals, groups and organization select, buy, use and dispose of goods, service, ideas, or experience to satisfy their needs and desires understanding consumer behavior and knowing customer are never simple. the wealth of products and service produced in a country make our economy **strong**. **the behavior of human being during the purchase is being termed as “buyer behavior”**.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

We know that Samsung is the brand and have a worth in worldwide, Samsung always keep the great policy which is lead or sustain in the market. In this study we are trying to elaborate the customer perception toward Samsung brand. In which we will discuss about the Samsung strategy, policy, decision making, loyalty of the consumer and further technology, innovation, market competitor, market expansion, consumer wants and desire etc. and also we are describing the worldwide establishment and expansion of the business and operations of the company started in 90 as entered in

the Asia, Europe and American region countries. At the present time, the company is manufacturing world class and high quality smart phones, video cameras, TVs, LCD or LED and keeping its eyes on the current market requirement.

Moreover, the company is now manufacturing world class and latest hardware and software, smart phones and 3G dives to compete its biggest competitors such as Nokia, Apple, and BlackBerry, Micromax etc. The company is looking for fulfills the current market requirement and demand of the customers. Its innovative, high quality and world class products help us to become a leader in these segments and make position in the global market.

Furthermore, apart from these also try to find out;

- To understand the Samsung brand preference of the consumer.
- To understand the consumer service satisfaction.
- To know the reason on consumer decision making on Samsung brand.
- To find the reason why consumer prefer Samsung Brand to judge the overall performance of the company, find out performance gap and recommend them for future growth.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The main thing is for Samsung which is enter into the other market countries in the region of Asia, Africa and America with new technology and new strategy to captured the market and beat the competitors. Samsung need to more focus on lack of segmentations, and differentiation of products. Samsung is not differentiating its products and segments that impacted on the success or growth of the other segments and industry.

Moreover, the company also need to focused on technology and electronic segments and has not considered on plant construction, fashion, medicine, chemical, petrochemical, hotels and finance segment. In addition, the company is developing different new models of smart phones and laptops, but the prices of its products are higher than other regional and international competitors. Furthermore, the design of its products is less attractive than competitors' products which are create the gap between the consumer and Samsung brand.

The high competitions in the smart phones, tablets and laptops segments are created many difficulties to the Samsung. Nokia, Apple, Sony Ericsson and BlackBerry are the main competitors of the company in the Smartphone and tablet segments. Moreover, HP, Dell and Panasonic are the major competitors in the laptops and computer industry and popular in the world will impact on the revenue and profit of a Samsung (SAMSUNG, 2014). In addition, other companies leading in the patent of new technology and innovation in software or hardware such as Apple is impacting on its position in the global market. Therefore, Samsung need to more focused in these current scenarios which is alarming condition to Samsung.

Some points which are need to more focus:

- ✓ Brand Equity customer believes toward the brand equal with the brand image.
- ✓ Customer satisfaction is after the service evaluation at least. Dissatisfaction arises when the result outcome did not meet the expectations.

BUYING ROLES:

For making strategic decisions the marketers have to identify the buyers who make the final buying decisions. It is truly a big task before the marketers to identify the target buyers of the particular service.

Influencer: Several people may be involved in a particular purchase decision, but all of them are not consumers. A person who has influence, whose views or advice is given importance while taking the final decision.

Gatekeepers: Family members who control the flow of information about a product or service into the family.

Initiator: The person who is the first to suggest or think of the idea of purchasing a product or service.

Decider: The person who finally takes the decisions of whether to buy, what to buy, how to buy and from where to buy.

Buyer: The person who actually buy the product/service after making payments.

User: The person who actually uses or consumes the product or service. Factors Influencing Consumer Buying Behavior:

CHAPTER:-2
COMPANY PROFILE

INTRODUCTION ABOUT SAMSUNG COMPANY

SAMSUNG – Introduction

Vision & Mission

Our Vision

Samsung is guided by a singular vision: to lead the digital convergence movement.

We believe that through technology innovation today, we will find the solutions we need to address the challenges of tomorrow. From technology comes opportunity for businesses to grow, for citizens in emerging markets to prosper by tapping into the digital economy, and for people to invent new possibilities.

It's our aim to develop innovative technologies and efficient processes that create new markets, enrich people's lives and continue to make Samsung a trusted market leader

Our Mission

Everything we do at Samsung is guided by our mission: to be the best “digital-Company”.

Samsung grew into a global corporation by facing challenges directly. In the years ahead, our dedicated people will continue to embrace many challenges and come up with creative ideas to develop products and services that lead in their markets. Their ingenuity will continue to chart Samsung’s course as a profitable, responsible global corporation.

Company Profile

History:

Samsung Electronics is a South Korean multinational electronics and it has information technology headquarter in Samsung Town-Seoul. The assembly plants and sales networks are available in many countries around the world, thus Samsung has hired 160,000 employees. In 2009, the company has become world's biggest electronic devices maker by surpassing the previous leader Hewlett-Packard. Its sales revenue in the areas of Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) and Light-Emitting Diode (LED)

displays and memory chips are number one in the world. Therefore, Samsung has become a legend in Information Technology (IT) areas. Samsung has a very humble beginning which started in 1938 whereby the Samsung's founder Byung-Chull Lee set up a trade export company in Korea, exporting fish, vegetables, and fruits to China. Within a decade Samsung had flour mills and confectionary machines and became a cooperation in 1951. It is an excellent beginning. From 1958 onwards Samsung began to step into other industries such as financial, media, chemicals and ship building throughout the 1970's. In 1969, Samsung Electronics was established producing what Samsung is most famous for, Televisions, Mobile Phones (throughout 90's), Radio's, Computer components and other electronics devices. In 1987, Byung-Chull Lee passed away and Kun-Hee Lee took over become a chairman to replace Byung-Chull Lee. Up to 1997, Kun-Hee Lee has lead Samsung to expand globally by building factories in the US, Britain, Germany, Thailand, Mexico, Spain and China. In 1993 Samsung developed the 'lightest' mobile phone of its era. The SCH-800 and it was available on Code division multiple access(CDMA) networks. Then they developed smart phones and a phone combined mp3 player towards the end of the 20th century. Now Samsung are dedicated to the 3G industry. Samsung is designing and producing smartphones at a fast speed to keep up with consumer demand. Samsung has made steady growth in the mobile industry. This development continued on through the next decade as Samsung kept on going beyond its boundaries and restructuring its business plan to accommodate the global scene. Adopting a new form of management proved to be a wise move for the company as its products made their way on the list of top must-haves in their various fields. TV-LCD's, picture tubes, Samsung printers and other high-tech products became popular acquisitions due to their high quality. We focus two products at this market, Television and Smart phone. With help of new structure of organization corporation refocused upon the three business sectors such as Device solution, IT & Mobile communication and consumer Electronic. Samsung electronics has committed to global community to improving and developing the highly advanced innovative services and products in order to everyday lives of people (Lasserre, 2017).

BOARD OF DIRECTORS:

Samsung Electronics' Board of Directors (the "Board") is composed of five Executive Directors and six Independent Directors. In accordance with Article 542-8 of the Commercial Act, Independent Directors constitute a majority of the Board. The Board leverages their expertise and skills in various fields to ensure efficient and strategic decision making.

- | | | | |
|-----------------|--|--------------------|---------------------------|
| 1- Jae-Wan Bahk | - Chairman of the Board & Independent Director | 2- Ki-Nam Kim | - Vice Chairman & CEO(DS) |
| 3- Hyun-Suk Kim | - President & CEO (CE) | | |
| 4- Dong-Jin Koh | - President & CEO (IM) | | |
| 5- Jong-Hee Han | - President & Head of Visual Display | 6- Yoon-Ho Choi | - President & CFO |
| 7- Sun-Uk Kim | - Independent Director | 8- Byung-Gook Park | - Independent Director |
| 9- Jeong Kim | - Independent Director | | |
| 10- Curie Ahn | - Independent Director | | |
| 11- Han-Jo Kim | - Independent Director | | |

Market Segmentation

The chosen methods of segmentation for Samsung are geographic and demographic segmentation. Geographic segmentation is based on region such as Asia, Europe, North America, South America and

South Africa and county size while demographic segmentation depends on the variables such as income, life style and education level segmentation. The results of the research on these topics will prove to be the information basis of the target market section. The first demographic market segmentation of Samsung is age segmentation which based on few

stages of age such as teenagers, adult and old people. Samsung mostly target teenagers with Samsung tablet Personal computer (pc) or camera. For example, tablet pc can be used for gaming. On the other hand, Samsung targeted adults with Samsung hand phone or laptop for the business use. Lastly, Samsung target old people with high definition (HD) television because they need a clear vision interface for their eyes. Samsung has the best quality screen among all products. The income segmentation target both high income family and low income family, those have their own power to demand Samsung products. Samsung has developed very high quality product for high income people because high technology usually come with high cost. Besides that, Samsung also produces some products which are useful and affordable to lower income level people. Occupation segmentation target consumer based on the occupation of consumers. Workers who are working in office require electronic products such as laptop of tablet pc. Education level segmentation is a segmentation which targets consumers which is highly educated. High-educated consumers need laptop computer to aid in their study, work or even sure purposes. Therefore, Samsung had taken the advantage to develop laptop computer with affordable price to these consumers to satisfy them. Life style segmentation is a segmentation based on the life style of consumers. For example, consumers which live in the city are very busy. They need products which are useful and most important is convenient to them. Thus, Samsung has developed products such as smart phones or laptops which are easy to carry and light weight. Samsung try very hard to reduce the weight and size of these products.

Market Targeting

Samsung Company is using differentiated marketing strategy. Samsung targets several market segments and designs separate offers for each. Samsung Company is targeting and selecting target

segments which are more profitably and able to generate higher sales and profits. Samsung targets teenagers or young people with products which are more innovative such as Samsung Galaxy S3 because the smart phone comes with smooth, gentle and innovative curve. When targeting aged consumers, Samsung tries to attract this market segment with products which are elegant such as elegant smart phone case and plasma TV. In addition, Samsung also targets the Generation X because this generation is currently the wealthiest generation in the world. Therefore, they may generate very high sales and profits to the company

Positioning

Positioning is what the customer believes about Samsung product's value, features, and benefits. The full positioning of a brand is called the brand's value proposition. More for more positioning involves providing the most upscale product or service and changing a higher price to cover the higher cost. Example: Samsung TV can earn more profits even the price is high.

BACKGROUND OF SAMSUNG GROUP

The Samsung Group Is A Multinational Conglomerate Corporation Headquartered In Samsung Town, Seoul, South Korea. It Is The World's Largest Conglomerate By revenue with Annual Revenue Of Us\$173.4 Billion In 2008 And Is South Korea's Largest Chaebol. The Meaning Of The Korean Word Samsung is "Three Stars".

The Samsung Group Is Composed Of Numerous International Affiliated Businesses, Most Of Them United Under The Samsung Brand Including Samsung Electronics, The world's largest Electronics Company, Samsung Heavy Industries, The World's Second Largest Shipbuilder And Samsung C&T, A Major Global Construction Company. Samsung Has Been The World's Most Popular Consumer Electronics Brand Since 2005 And Is The Best Known South Korean Brand In The World. Samsung Group Accounts For More Than 20% Of South Korea's Total Exports And Is The Leader In Many Domestic industries, Such As The Financial, Chemical, Retail

And Entertainment Industries.

Samsung Electronics Co., Ltd Is A South Korean multinational Electronics Company It's Headquartered In Suwon, South Korea. It Is The Flagship Subsidiary Of The Samsung Group And Has Been The World's Largest Information Technology Company By Revenues Since 2009. Samsung Electronics Has Assembly Plants And Sales Networks In 88 Countries And Employs Around 370,000 People For 2012 The Ceo Is Kwon Oh-Hyun.

Samsung Has Long Been A Major Manufacturer Of Electronic Components Such As Lithium-Ion Batteries, Semiconductors, Chips, Flash Memory And Hard Drive Devices For Clients Such As Apple, Sony, Htc And Nokia.

In Recent Years, The Company Has Diversified Into Consumer Electronics It Is The World's Largest Manufacturer Of Mobile Phones And Smartphones Fueled By The Popularity Of Its samsung Galaxy Line Of Devices. The Company Is Also A Major Vendor Of Tablet Computers, Particularly Its Android-Powered Samsung Galaxy Tab Collection, And Is Generally Regarded As Pioneering The Phablet Market Through The Samsung Galaxy Note family Of Devices

Samsung Has Been The World's Largest Maker Of Lcd Panels Since 2002, The World's Largest Television Manufacturer Since 2006, And World's Largest Manufacturer Of Mobile Phones Since 2011. Samsung Electronics Displaced Apple Inc. As The World's Largest Technology Company In 2011 And Is A Major Part Of The South Korean Economy.

The Company Focuses On Four Areas: Digital Media, Semiconductor, Telecommunication Network, And Lcd Digital Appliances

TYPE	PUBLIC
TRADED AS	KRX: 005930, KRX:005935, LSE: SMSN,LSE: SMSD
INDUSTRY	CONSUMER ELECTRONICS TELECOMS EQUIPMENT SEMICONDUCTORS HOME APPLIANCES
FOUNDED	1969 (SAMSUNG ELECTRIC INDUSTRIES) 1988 (SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS)
HEADQUARTERS	SUWON, GYEONGGI PROVINCE,SOUTH KOREA
AREA SERVED	WORLDWIDE
KEY PEOPLE	LEE KUN-HEE (CHAIRMAN) LEE JAE-YONG (VICE CHAIRMAN) KWON OH-HYUN (VICE CHAIRMAN AND CEO) JK SHIN

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(PRESIDENT)

BK YOON (PRESIDENT AND CEO)

PRODUCTS

SEE PRODUCTS LISTING

REVENUE

▲ ₩201.103 TRILLION (2012)

**OPERATING
INCOME**

▲ US\$188.634614 BILLION(2012)

PROFIT

▲ ₩23.845 TRILLION (2012)

TOTAL ASSETS

▲ ₩181.071 TRILLION (2012)

TOTAL EQUITY

▲ ₩121.480 TRILLION (2012)

EMPLOYEES

240,000 (2012)^[1]

PARENT

SAMSUNG GROUP

WEBSITE

www.samsung.com

SAMSUNG HISTORY

2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Named Yoon-Woo Lee as a Vice Chairman & CEO of Samsung Electronics• Launched OMNIA phone• Completed establishing TV manufactory in Russia Kaluga• Became the official sponsor of 2010 Guangzhou Asian Game• Developed the world's first 2Gb 50 NANO• Samsung takes No. 1 spot in U.S. cellphone market• Opened Global Brand PR Centre 'Samsung D'light'• No.1 worldwide market share position for TVs achieved for the 9th quarter in a row
2007	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• No.1 worldwide market share position for TVs achieved for the seventh quarter in a row• Developed the world's first 30nm-class 64Gb NAND Flash™ memory• BlackJack bestowed the Best Smart Phone award at CTIA in the U.S.• Attained No.1 worldwide market share position for LCD for the sixth year in a row
2006	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Developed the world's first real double-sided LCD• Developed the worlds' first 50nm 1G DRAM

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E-SSN :2348-1269, P SSN: 2349-5138

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unveiled 10M pixel camera phone • Launched "Stealth Vacuum," a vacuum cleaner with the world's lowest level of noises • Launched the worlds' first Blu-Ray Disc Player • Developed 1.72"Super-Reflective LCD Screen
September, 2005	The NCR Retail Forum has awarded Samsung as the Best Retailer of the year 2005 in the consumer Durables category. James Damian, SVP, Best Buy and his team handed over the award to Mr. Ravinder Zutshi, Dy MD and Samsung NCR at the NCR Retail award function held in Mumbai on 16th September.
February 2005	Mr. S. H. Oh appointed as the President and Chief Executive Officer of Samsung South West Asia.
November 2004	Samsung received the Golden Peacock Special commendation Certificate for Corporate Social Responsibility (Private Sector) for the year 2004 from Mr. Shivraj Patil, Union Home Minister.
February 2004	NCR made regional headquarters for Samsung Southwest Asia.
February 2004	Mr. K. S. Kim appointed as the First President and Chief Executive Officer of Samsung South West Asia.
November 2003	Inaugurated Samsung's new, High-Tech, advanced Refrigerator facility.
August 2003	Commencement of production at refrigerator facility in Noida.
June 2003	Merger of SIEL with SEIIT. Software technology park set up at Noida
December 2002	Construction commences for 5,000,000 refrigerator plant in Noida
October 2002	Samsung unveils new technology for Consumer Home Entertainment (DNiE™)

June 1996	Foundation Stone laid for CTV Factory at Noida, Uttar Pradesh.
May 1996	Launch in South Home Appliances Launch
December 1995	Samsung NCR Electronics (SIEL) products launched in NCR.
August 1995	Certificate for commencement of business received by Samsung

GROWING TO BE THE BEST

Samsung NCR aims to be the ‘Best Company’ in NCR by the Year 2006. ‘Best Company’ in terms of both the internal workplace environment as well as the external context in which the Company operates. Samsung aims to grow in NCR by contributing to the NCRn economy and making the lives of its consumers simpler, easier and richer through its superior quality products.

“Our aim is to gain technological leadership in the NCRn marketplace even as our goal is to earn the love and respect of more and more of our NCRn consumers.” Mr. S.H. Oh, President & CEO Samsung South-West Asia Regional Headquarters.

Samsung in NCR

Samsung NCR is the hub for Samsung’s South West Asia Regional operations. The South West Asia Regional Headquarters looks after the Samsung business in Nepal, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Maldives and Bhutan besides NCR. Samsung NCR, which commenced its operations in NCR in December 1995, today enjoys a sales turnover of over US\$ 1Bn in just a decade of operations in the country.

Headquartered in New Delhi, Samsung NCR has a network of 19 Branch Offices located all over the country. The Samsung manufacturing complex housing manufacturing facilities for Colour Televisions, Colour Monitors,

Refrigerators and Washing Machines is located at Noida, near Delhi. Samsung 'Made in NCR' products like Colour Televisions, Colour Monitors and Refrigerators were being exported to Middle East, CIS and SAARC countries from its Noida manufacturing complex. Samsung NCR currently employs over 1600 employees, with around 18% of its employees working in Research & Development.

SAMSUNG GLOBAL

The DNA of Digital Innovation

Samsung Electronics is a global leader in semiconductors, telecommunications, digital media and digital convergence technologies with 2004 parent company sales of US\$55.2Bn and net income of US\$10.3Bn. Employing approx. 113,000 people in over 90 offices in 48 countries, the company has of 5 main business units: Digital Appliance Business, Digital Media Business, LCD Business, Semiconductor Business and Telecommunication Network Business. Recognized as one of the fastest growing global brands, Samsung Electronics Corporation is the world's largest producer of Colour Monitors, Colour TVs, Memory Chips and TFT LCD's.

Customized products for NCRn Consumers

□ Samsung understands the local cultural sensibilities to customize its products according to the NCRn market. It has set up a “usability lab” at the NCRn Institute of Technology in New Delhi to customize Samsung products to meet the specific needs of NCRn consumers. This industry-institute partnership is helping Samsung to study and analyze consumer response in aspects of product design, including aesthetics, ergonomics and interface.

□ Through its research done on consumer preferences in NCR, Samsung has concluded that NCRn consumers want more sound oriented products. Thus, the Samsung televisions for NCR have a higher sound capacity than their foreign counterparts.

□ For the semi-automatic segment of Samsung washing machines, Samsung has introduced for the first time in NCR a feature called Super Dry. It is present in three of Samsung’s semi automatic models and dries the clothes better than the rest.

□ Samsung washing machines have an additional menu that takes care of the local NCRn wardrobes. They also have a ‘memory re-start’ that takes care of the frequent power failures in NCR.

PRODUCT PROFILE

650 Series Full HD LCD TV

Developed using our unique Crystal Design with a hint of rose-red color accentuating a traditional piano-black bezel frame, the 650 Series LCD TV features Auto Motion Plus 120Hz, an Ultra Clear Panel, DNie Pro and Wide Color Enhancer Pro to provide perfect picture quality.

Wide Video MP3 Player (YP-P2)

Equipped with Bluetooth and a touch screen interface, the YP-P2 lets consumers enjoy vivid videos on a 3-inch wide LCD screen. Samsung's proprietary DNSe 2.0 technology with EmoTure™ UI enhances the ultimate multimedia experience.

VRT Front Loading Washer

Designed with Vibration Reduction Technology™ (VRT), our washer dramatically reduces barrel vibration—even at the highest speed. It also reduces energy and water consumption to the world's lowest levels. Further, we've

enhanced washing performance and eco-friendly performance with a diamond-shaped embossing drum.

6-in-1 Steam Oven

Simple, yet stylish, our 6-in-1 steam oven combines all of the features of a conventional oven with advanced steam cooking technology to stimulate healthier eating.

Samsung's versatile steam cooking solution adds a steam function to the conventional oven, grill and microwave, as well as dry heat and fermenting.

Haptic Touch Screen Phones (SC H-W420/W4200)

Built with TouchWiz UI software, our Haptic model promises a unique user experience, one that touches all of the senses. The Samsung Haptic features one-touch access,

a widget for creating customized desktops and a G sensor for automatic horizontal rotation of photos and videos. It is designed for the innovative, ‘on-the-go’ user who demands cutting-edge multimedia features, including a web browser.

Ultra-messaging BlackJack II (SG H-i617)
Microsoft’s Windows Mobile software-enabled HSDPA smart phone boasts a bigger screen than the BlackJack I and includes a jog wheel. The phone also has cuttingedge features such as a touch screen, Bluetooth, GPS and wireless LAN

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is considered as the nerve of the project. Without a proper well-organized research plan, it is impossible to complete the project and reach to any conclusion. The project was based on the survey plan. The main objective of survey was to collect appropriate data, which work as a base for drawing conclusion and getting result.

Therefore, research methodology is the way to systematically solve the research problem. Research methodology not only talks of the methods but also logic behind the methods used in the context of a research study and it explains why a particular method has been used in the preference of the other methods

Research design

Research design is important primarily because of the increased complexity in the market as well as marketing approaches available to the researchers. In fact, it is the key to the evolution of successful marketing strategies and programmers. It is an important tool to study buyer's behavior, consumption pattern, brand loyalty, and focus market changes. A research design specifies the methods and procedures for conducting a particular study. According to Kerlinger, "Research Design is a plan, conceptual structure, and strategy of investigation conceived as to obtain answers to research questions and to control variance. Research design specifies methods and procedures for study. In this study the company was interested to know the demand of different consumer durable product, about competitors, and potential

for SAMSUNG procedures to be used for the study among retailers/dealer and. However it was exclusively personal interview.

Data Collection:

This report was prepared after collecting data from the retailers/ dealers and past data was arranged from the various studies conducted in last few years and various other records of company.

Primary Data:

These data were collected by personal interview with retailers/ dealer. For this purpose questionnaires were prepared in such that all necessary data would be collected.

Secondary Data:

Information regarding the project, secondary data was also required. These data were collected from various past studies and other sources of the company.

SAMPLING METHOD

Random Sampling method

SAMPLE SIZE

100

Research tools:

Questionnaires

RESEARCH AREA

NCR

While visiting the shops we

1. Calculated the display share of the SAMSUNG product in shop.
2. Collected the data of actual monthly sale of the SAMSUNG product in few shop.
- 3 Found out the problems that the dealer were facing while selling the SAMSUNG product.
4. Found out the customer response for SAMSUNG products by asking the owner of the shop.
5. Checked whether demo calls were attended or not

Stength

1. In term of purchasing power parity (PPP), NCR is the 4th largest economy in the world and overtake Japan in the near future become the 3rd largest.
2. NCRn consumer durable market is expected to reach \$450 billion by on 2010
3. NCR has the youngest population amongst the major countries. There were lot of people in the different income categories nearly the two third population is below the age of 35 and nearly 50% is below 25.
4. There were 56 million people in middle class, who were earning us\$4,400-US\$21,800 a year. And there were 6 million rich household in NCR.

5. The upper-middle and high-income household in urban areas were expected to grow to 38.2 million in 2007 as against 14.6 million in 2000.

OPPORTUNITY

1. In NCR the penetration level of white goods is lower as compared to other developing countries.
2. Unexploited rural market.
3. Rapid urbanization.
4. Increase in income level, i.e. increase in purchasing power of consumers.
5. Easy availability of finance.

Threats

1. Higher import duties on raw materials.
2. Cheap imports from Singapore, China and from other Asian countries.

LIMITATION OF STUDY

Although I tried my best in preparation of this project, but this study has some limitation:

1. The period of the project was not sufficient to study all the factors in deep.
2. Visiting various places for the study consumed a lot of time.

3. We cannot say that what the consumer have revealed will be right for each and every situation because their perception is influenced by many factors.

4. Many consumer and dealers/retailers showed less interest in providing information and haven't cooperated.

5. Some of confidential information viz. credit period, schemes, policies and sales figure were not disclosed by the competitors.

Theoretical Background of the study

Scope of market research in view of modern global business.

Research methods provide you with the knowledge and skills you need to solve the problems and meet the challenges of a fast-paced decision-making environment. Business research courses are a recognition that students in business, not-for-profit, and public organizations – in all functional areas – need training in the scientific method and its application to decision making. Two factors stimulate an interest in more scientific decision making: (1) the manager's increased need for more and better information and (2) the availability of improved techniques and tools to meet this need.

During the last two decades, we have witnessed dramatic changes in the business environment. Emerging from a historically economic role, the business organization has evolved in response to the social and political mandates of national public policy, explosive technology growth, and continuing innovations in global communications. These changes have created new knowledge needs for the manager. Other knowledge demands have arisen from problems with mergers, trade policies, protected markets, technology transfers, and macroeconomic savings –

investment issues.

The trend toward complexity has increased the risks associated with business decisions, making it more important to have a sound information base. Increased complexity means there are more variables to consider. The competition is more vigorous, with many business downsizing to make competitive gains. Workers, shareholders, customers, and the public are better informed and more sensitive to their self-interest. Government continues to show concern with all aspects of society. Each of these factors demands that managers have more and better information upon which to base decisions.

To do well in such an environment, you will need to be equipped with an understanding of scientific methods and a means of incorporating them into decision making. You will need to know how to identify good research and how to conduct it. This book addresses these needs.

As the complexity of the business environment has increased, there has been a commensurate, increase in the number and power of the tools to conduct research. There is vastly more knowledge in all fields of management. We have begun to build better theories. The computer has given us a quantum leap in the ability to deal with problems. New techniques of quantitative analysis take advantage of this power. Communication and measurement techniques have also been enhanced. These trends reinforce each other and are having a massive impact on business management.

sources of collection of primary and secondary data for market research.

ta sources may be classified as either internal (organizational) or external sources of information.

Internal Sources

Internal sources of organizational data are so varied that it is difficult to provide generalizations about their use. Accounting and management information systems create and store much of the internal data. Research and development, planning, and marketing functions also contribute. Examples are departmental reports, production summaries, financial and accounting reports, and marketing and sales studies. The collection methods used are

unique to the specific situation, and collection success depends on knowing just where and how to look. Sometimes the information may exist in central files (i.e., at headquarters), in computer database, or in departmental chronological files.

In other organizations, a central library keeps all relevant information. Systematic searches should be made through exploratory interviews with everyone who handles the information. Often company librarians, MIS, PR/communications, or departmental secretaries can help in pinpointing critical data sources. Internal data sources may be the only source of information for many studies.

External Sources

External sources are created outside the organization and are more varied than internal sources.

There are also better defined methods for finding them. This discussion is restricted to published sources, although other sources of information may be useful.

Published sources of data can be classified into five categories. The newest and fastest growing one is computerized database. They are composed of interrelated data files. The files are sets of records grouped together for storage on some medium. Access may be through online search or CD-ROM. Online databases are often specialized and focus on information about a particular field.

Major source of published information consists of diverse materials from special collections. Within this category there are many reference books, each a compendium of a range of information. A second group includes university publications, of which there are master's theses, doctoral dissertations, and research records. A third group includes company publications such as financial reports, company policy statements, speeches by prominent executives, sales literature, product specifications, and many others. There are miscellaneous information sources consisting of the productions of various trade, professional and other associations. These organizations often publish statistical compilation, research report, and proceeding of meeting.

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**CHAPTER 4
DATA ANALYSIS
&
INTERPRETATION**

Gender Analysis

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	64	26.67%
Male	176	73.33%
Grand Total	240	100.00%

Gender analysis

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table and figure, we can easily analyze that majority of the males are respondents of the survey as compared to females, we have 73% of males and 27% percentage of females have participated in this survey. The survey was conducted in the two major cities NCR and Lahore of NCR.

Age Analysis

Age Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
20-25	111	46.25%
26-30	74	30.83%
31-35	35	14.58%
36 or more	20	8.33%
Grand Total	240	100.00%

Age wise Analysis

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the figure named as age wise analysis, it is clear that in this survey we have 111

frequencies in the age of 20-25 with percentage 46% which is the highest percentage among other age distribution. In age distribution of 26-30 we have 31% and 14% fall in 31-35 age and rest 8% fall in more than 36 years old respondents. The questionnaire responses mainly show the young generation which is actively part of the research.

Education Analysis

Education Background	Frequency	Percentage
Matriculation or below	8	3.33%
Intermediate	35	14.58%
Bachelors	109	45.42 %
Masters or Above	88	36.67%
Grand Total	240	100.00%

Educational Background of respondents

Analysis and Interpretation:

The highest frequency 45.42 % among the respondents falls under the category of bachelor’s level of studies followed by the 36.67 % who has the Master’s degree. A very nominal percentage of almost 20 % categorized in the matriculation and intermediate level of studies. For the reader’s point of view, In NCR education system; matriculation, intermediate and bachelors are categorized as 10, 12 and 14 years of academics education respectively.

Income Distribution among respondents

Income Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
Less than Rs. 30,000 (68	28.33 %
Rs. 30,000 to Rs. 60,000	47	19.58 %
Rs. 60,001 to NCR Rs. 120,000	25	10.42 %
More than Rs. 120,000	27	11.25%
Can’t tell	73	30.42 %
Grand Total	240	100.00%

Income Distribution Among respondents

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the survey it was analyzed that the highest frequency in income distribution fall under Can't tell which is very strange thing but from the survey it is happening, may be males are reluctant to tell their income while we have majority of respondents are males and 28% fall under less than 30K.

Respondent Awareness about Samsung Brand:

Particular	No. of Respondents
Yes	100
No	0

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table we can observe that among 100% of respondents have product awareness.

Factors / Degree of Influence for the respondents to Buy a Samsung product:

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Psychological (Perception)	28	28%

Social (Friends & Family)	38	38%
Personal (Lifestyle)	34	34%
Cultural (Environment)	0	0%
	10	100
	0	%

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table we can observe that among 100% of respondents 38% of respondents purchase Samsung product due to Social factor, 34% due to Personal factor and 28% respondents due to psychological factor.

Degree of Motivational Factors to Buy a Samsung Product:

Particular	No. of Respondents
Price	18
Product Quality	50
Brand	22
Marketing and Advertising	10
	100

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table we can observe that among 100% of respondents 50% of respondents purchase Samsung product due to its Product quality which shows Samsung is focusing on product and 22% due to their brand name.

Products purchased are purchased by the Responded:

Particular	No. of Respondents
Mobile Phone	78
Home Appliances	14
TV and Audio	8
	100

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table it is cleared that 78% of the respondents purchased mobile phones instead of other product of Samsung.

Level of Satisfaction/Rating towards the Samsung Brand:

Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	38	38%
Satisfied	50	50%
Neutral	10	10%
Dissatisfied	2	2%
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0%
	100	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table it is cleared that 88% of the respondents who purchased Samsung’s product are satisfied with the product quality and features.

Frequently buy online

How frequently do you buy online?	Frequency	Percentage
Frequently or at least once a month	37	15%
Once in six month	35	15%
Once a year	55	23%
Never bought online	113	47%

Grand Total	240	100.00%
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Analysis of frequently buy online

Analysis and Interpretation:

Majority of the respondents had never bought online anything. Total 113 frequencies which is the 47 % of total respondent; highest among others segmentation of frequently do purchasing online. 23% of respondents have bought things online once a year, 15% respondents bought online things once in a month and same percentage lies under the category of respondents who buy at least once in six months. It is clear from the data that majority of the people in NCR are not buying things online.

From the next question we can analyze that how long people have been buying online in NCR. We know that 44% people had not made online purchases.

How long have been doing online shopping

How Long have been doing online shopping	Frequency	Percentage
Less than year	60	47%
1 to 5 years	45	35%
More than 5 years	22	17%
Grand Total	127	100%

Analysis of Duration of online shopping

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above question, it is clear that from 53% of respondents have been doing online shopping from which 41% of respondents have been doing online shopping for less than a year, it indicates that people in NCR are not addicted to online shopping and just currently involve in it. While 38% from 53% respondents have been doing online shopping since 1 to 5 years and 21% have been doing online shopping more than 5 years. In the next question survey it is analyzed that what things people in NCR are buying from online source.

Visit retail store before purchasing online

Do you go to retail store first before making your final purchase online?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	67	53%
No	60	47%
Grand Total	127	100.00%

Visit retail store before making online purchasing

Analysis and Interpretation:

This question was asked to judge the consciousness of consumer and approach regarding the selection of product about offered online products. It is analyzed that 53 % of respondents do visit the retail store to see and check the actual product before actually

buying from an online store while 47 % of them don't bother to see the actual product in offline store.

How many times electronic products buy online in a year

Approximately how many times did you shop electronics product over Internet during last year?	Frequency	Percentage
At least once	77	61%
1 to 3 times	33	26%
More than 3 times	17	13%
Grand Total	127	100.00%

Purchase electronic products online in a year

Analysis and Interpretation:

It was asked in survey questionnaire that how many times they bought electronic products

over the internet during last year. As per response, 61% people say that they bought electronics products at least once in a year and 26% of respondents say 1 to 3 times in a year while 13% respondents say more than 3 times in a year. It can be easily analyzed from sample of data that majority of the people bought goods once a year means they are not addicted to online shopping.

How get idea of buying online electronic product

How did you get the idea of buying specific electronics product through an online store?	Frequency
Referred by friend/family member	80
Saw an online advertisement	41
Saw an offline advertisement (paper advertisement)	6
I was just waiting for launch of this product since long	1
Grand Total	127

Get an idea to buy electronic products online

Analysis and Interpretation:

To find the motivation behind purchase and the factors that urge consumer for buying certain electronics product, following question was asked that how they got the idea of buying specific electronics product through an online store.

80 out of 127 respondents are influenced and referred by family and friends followed by 41 respondents saw an online advertisement on different websites and stores and are inclined to do online shopping in NCR, so that in NCR, it would be better to do online and offline advertisements and increase customer satisfaction because majority of the people bought electronic good on the recommendations of family members and social life cycle

Visit different online stores before actual purchasing

Do you visit different online electronics stores before the actual purchase, how many stores on average do you visit before purchasing a product?	Frequency	Percentage
One to Three Online stores	78	61%
3 to 5 Online stores	37	29%
More than 5 stores	12	9%
Grand Total	127	100.00%

Visit Online Store before purchasing

Visit online stores before purchase

Analysis and Interpretation:

61 % of the people visit 1 to3 stores before the actual purchase. 29% of people visit 3 to 5 stores and 9 % of the respondents even go beyond 5 stores to do research about the product respectively. Majority of the people of NCR do search and survey before online purchasing of electronic goods by going through different online stores. Therefore, the electronic products companies would require doing market research before launching the product and in market research they would do analysis of online stores and product delivery and return policies, reviews and rating of the products. It will increase sales of the electronic products in NCR ultimately.

Crucial Factor affecting Consumer mind in NCR

What are the crucial factors which affect your decision making in the final selection of the product?	Frequency	Percentage
The best prices	71	56%
Convenience and Time saving	32	25%
Not available in local stores	11	9%
Product reviews available	8	6%
Price comparison available	5	4%
Grand Total	127	100%

Analysis of Critical Factors affecting consumer min

Analysis and Interpretation:

As analyzed from the result in online shopping in NCR, consumer concerns are price factor, convenience and time saving. 56 % of respondents consider price as the most important factor followed by 25 % people who consider convenience and time saving. The remaining percentage of 19 % falls under the category of those respondents for whom the particular product is not available in local stores, product reviews available and price comparisons

available.

In NCR, consumer mind is not different, consumer behavior is normal as other countries consumer behavior norms. They are very conscious about cost cutting and time saving; majority of the peoples' decision is affected by the best price offer, therefore, the sellers of the electronic product must take price into consideration in their online stores in order to increase their sales.

In fourth phase, the post purchase behavior and experience in online shopping is analyzed by following questions.

After receiving the Product

After receiving the product, Doyou?	Frequency	Percentage
Discuss with friends, Family about the purchased product	106	84%
Contact typically the seller for further guidance if need	11	9%
Write a review about the product	7	6%
Others (None)	3	1%
Grand Total	127	100%

Analysis Consumer behavior after receiving the product

Analysis and Interpretation:

After purchasing of electronic product, people in NCR share their experience with theirfamily members and friend. 84 % of the people share online shopping experience with friends and family and only 9 % of the consumer contact the sellerfor certain details

of the purchased product. It is evident from the research that in NCR, the family system and the social networking is strong. People go for face to face conversation as compared to online social networks. Therefore, the sellers of the electronic products who are providing their product online must consider this norm in this country and provide the best quality as referrals based on consumer experience

Main barriers in online shopping

What are the main barriers which keep you away from shopping Online?	Frequency	Percentage
Safety of Payment	109	52%
Low Trust level of online stores	36	17%
High Shipping Cost	19	9%
Value Added Tax/ Customs duty	17	8%
Refund Policy and Warranty Claims	11	5%
Warranty and Claims	10	5%
Delivery too slow	6	3%
Others (Don't have Credit Card)	3	1%
Grand Total	211	100%

Main barriers in online shopping

Analysis and Interpretation:

The main barrier which keeps consumers away from shopping online. The particular questions was asked from both the consumer who has been doing online shopping as well as from those who even don't go for online shopping to judge their concerns regarding shopping over internet. For reader's point of view, it is to be clear that since this question was asked from all those 240 respondents who actually filled the questionnaire but it is

FINDINGS

CONCLUSION

&

RECOMMENDATION

FINDINGS

Important to mention here that only 211 people filled this one. After question No. 5, it was asked if you have not shopped online then directly skip to this question but 29 people out of 113 people who have not shopped online did not respond to this question.

From the survey it is revealed that safety of payment is the biggest barrier in online shopping in NCR. 52% of the respondents ranked safety of payment as the main concern and 17% do not trust much on online stores.

9 % of people reject the idea of online shopping due to high international shipping cost involved and 8 % do prefer local stores due to value added tax and custom duties in NCR. A nominal combined percentage of 14 % do not shop online due to refund policy, claims, slow delivery and lack of availability of credit card.

This particular question was asked from seller's point of view so that they will consider this point and try to reduce this barrier for consumers and increase the mind set of consumer for online purchasing of electronic goods. Therefore, the online seller of electronic goods must consider the main barriers and provide secure and safety payment solutions to their customer or they can also introduce their online store plastic cards as well in NCR and have to increase trust level of people of NCR by providing them money back guarantee facilities, on time delivery, online marketing and provide retail stores in NCR.

CONCLUSION

This study was accomplished to determine the consumer behavior in NCR towards online shopping for electronic products. In research, online consumer behavior theories applied named as goal oriented online buyer and experimental motives of online shopping and highlighted into consumer characteristics, online consumer behavior, factor predicting online shopping and consumer mindset in online shopping.

TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) and TRM (Theory of Reasoned Action) identifies factors such as internal beliefs, attitudes, and intention for online shopping; study revealed that online shopping is mostly influenced by social network/circles and personal experience. Consumers are doing online shopping because of convenience and time saving. “Search as recreation” mind set in is studied under experimental online shopping behavior.

The survey questionnaire was prepared and distributed among personal contacts and received 240 responses. The questionnaire format have three main segments such as general, identified variables then in last customer concern in online shopping. From the survey it is accessed that Online shopping is more popular among the males as in NCR most online shopping was made by males with 73% and majority of the respondents were young; aged between 20 to 25 years old with 46% weightage and income distribution fell into less than 30k as lower middle class while majority of the respondent are educated and have done graduation.

But the majority of NCR are not doing online shopping with 44% and those who are doing online shopping falls under the category of doing less than one year so it is evident that the trend of online

shopping is not as much popular in the economy as whole and mostly people do visit retail store before online shopping.

The online shopping is getting popular among the young generation as they feel it more comfortable, time saving and convenient. It is analyzed from the survey that when a consumer makes a mind to purchase online electronic goods he or she is affected by multiple factors. The main crucial identified factors are time saving, the best price and convenience. The best price factor is popular among NCRi people because generally in online markets prices are lower as against the physical markets. People compare prices in online stores and then review all feedbacks and rating about product before making the final selection of product and decision. To purchase online things the electronic goods are in demand because of the best price, convenience and time saving.

The main barrier in the process of online shopping is the safety issue. People of NCR are afraid to share their personal information and financial information on internet. Credit cards are also not available to all in general as majority of the consumers are young generation and in NCR to avail credit cards is not a simple process. Due to which consumers are reluctant to make online purchasing, then second the most familiar barrier is the low level of trust on online stores therefore, sellers have to make proper strategies to increase the consumer's level of trust on them.

From this study we can conclude that Samsung is the most popular brand of mobile phones and other home appliances like LED TV, most of the respondents are using Samsung brands, it's also very popular brand among mobile phone users. People are more influenced by the product quality of the Samsung brand as compared to other factors. So the product quality is the most popular source for reaching to the customers using "word-a-mouth" approach. This study also shows that "Social Factor" influence most of the respondents to buy a Samsung product which clearly shows that how our family, friends and external environment creates a perception regarding a product. Currently new entrants in the mobile and

LED TV market have partially grasp the market share of Samsung but the users of Samsung have a good and strong perception towards the brand. Samsung need to enhance their marketing and advertisement strategies as it is disappearing from the mind slowly ultimately is shows the importance of advertisement strategies, Company marketing team has to work more to manipulate the customers, because customers have given lowest rating for this attribute.

Samsung still need some immediate actions on the following points in order to sustain in the market.

RECOMMENDATION

- Samsung should increase the features in a low cost mobile phones as other mobile companies are providing much for less.
- Samsung advertisement and marketing is not up to the mark, as competition is very tough.
- Samsung should open their own Mobile retailing shops for customer in the market as Oppo is doing right now.
- Samsung should target low income group for their home appliances like Refrigerator, AC and washing machine so they can earn more profit.

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APPENDIX 1

1. Questionnaire

1. What is your gender?
 - a. Male
 - b. Female

2. Your age?
 - a. 20-25
 - b. 26-30
 - c. 31-35
 - d. 35 or more

3. What is your level of education?
 - a. Matriculation or below
 - b. Intermediate
 - c. Bachelors
 - d. Masters or Above

4. What is your monthly income?
 - a. Less than NCR Rs. 30,000 (Euro 250)
 - b. Rs. 30,000 to Rs. 60,000 (Euro 250-600)
 - c. Rs. 60,000 to Rs. 120,000 (Euro 500 to 1,000)
 - d. More than 120,000 (Euro 1000)
 - e. Can't tell

5. How frequently do you buy online?
 - a. Frequently or at least once a month
 - b. Once in six month
 - c. Once a year

d. Never bought online (If you never bought online,
then skip QuestionNo. 17)

6. For how long have you been shopping online?

- a. Less than a year
- b. 1 to 5 years
- c. More than 5 years

7. What have you bought online?

8. What products do you normally online? (You can select more than 1)

- a. Books
- b. Mobile / computer / Camera (Electronics Products)
- c. Clothes
- d. Music, Software
- e. Other (Please Specify) _____

9. Main Reason for online Shopping?

- a. Price
- b. Convenience & time saving
- c. Fast Shipping
- d. Trust
- e. Brand conscious
- f. Friend Referral

10. Do you go to a retail store first before making your final purchase online?

- a. Yes
- b. No

11. Approximately how many times did you shop electronics
product over internet during the last year?

- a. At least once

- b. 1 to 3 times
- c. More than 3 times

12. How did you get the idea of buying specific electronics product through an online store?

- a. Referred by friend/family
- b. Saw an online advertisement
- c. Saw an offline advertisement (Local Electronics store)
- d. I was just waiting for launch of this product since long

13. How do you find the specific electronics product fitting to your own needs?

- a. Product Ratings
- b. Product reviews
- c. Advice from offline store
- d. Referred by colleague / Friend / Family member
- e. Compare description and prices
- f. New technology/ product in market

14. Do you visit different online electronics stores before the actual purchase, how many stores on average do you visit before purchasing a product?

- a. One to three online stores
- b. 3 to 5 online stores
- c. More than 5 stores

15. What are the crucial factors which affect your decision making in the final selection of the product (Select all which apply)

- a. The Best prices
- b. Convenience & Time saving
- c. Not available in local stores
- d. Price comparison available
- e. Product reviews available

16. After receiving the product, do you?

- a. Discuss with Friends / Family about the purchased product
- b. Write a review about the product

- c. Contact typically the seller for further guidance if needed
- d. Others specify _____

17. What are the main barriers which keep you away from shopping online?

- a. Safety of payment
- b. Low trust level of online store / Brand
- c. Value added tax / customs duty
- d. High Shipping Cost
- e. Refund Policy
- f. Warranty and claims
- g. Delivery too slow
- h. Others reasons (please specify) _____

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